

VIRTIGATION – Emerging viral diseases in tomatoes and cucurbits: Implementation of mitigation strategies for durable disease management

Deliverable Nr. 5.5 Results from field testing of plant extracts

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1 PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY

Experimental tests have been realised in semi-field and in field environment to screen a selection of plant extracts with insecticidal effects, developed in the frame of the project VIRTIGATION, for: i) their efficacy on whitefly vectors, especially *Bemisia spp.gr. tabaci*; ii) their selectivity on natural enemies (both parasitoids and predators), and iii) their side effects on pollinator insects. Tests have been realised by partners in Belgium, Germany, Italy and Spain, by comparing performance of the new plant derivate formulations not only to untreated controls and co-formulates alone, but also to insecticides commonly used in Europe for whitefly control, both synthetic and of natural origin. Although with some variability in the results and some exceptions whose understanding needs further studies, the tests realised show an appreciable control action by the new plant derivate formulations against *B. tabaci*, which is statistically comparable to other insecticides of plant origin already registered and used in Europe for whitefly control. All tested new bioinsecticide formulations showed also no remarkable side effects on natural enemies, especially on parasitoids, as well as on bumblebees. These results indicate the tested new bioinsecticides as good candidates for possible development and practical use in integrated control programs of whiteflies, although it is still necessary to better clarify some aspects related to their dosage for field use and their application strategy.